

H2020 - Research and Innovation Action

APPLICATE

Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: Modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

WP7: user engagement, dissemination and training aims to increase awareness of the impact of Arctic changes on weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere by developing relevant forms of communication to spread the project results to maximise the exposure of the science produced to end-users and the public at large.

To achieve this objective, WP7 has from the start of the project, developed outreach material, as per deliverable D7.5. The WP has and will continuously update and add as relevant outreach materials targeted at various specific audiences that will be disseminated by the projects outreach team and its communication channels such as the project website and social media, by project partners on the occasion of seminars, conferences and at appropriate public exhibitions.

Dissemination materials are maintained and available to the public and project partners to use through the project website and / or its internal document management system. These include: the project logo, the project website, social media outputs (Facebook and Twitter), a project flyer, a rollup poster and an introductory presentation of the project as well as all other project deliverables.

New additions since deliverable D7.5 in May 2017 include:

- A project poster template for use at conferences.
- A blog, in close cooperation with the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP), was launched on 1st September. Already several very valuable articles by key Arctic stakeholders have been published as a result of the APPLICATE partnership.
- Two webinars organised in cooperation with the Association for Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS). The first was focused on introducing the project and was given by Thomas Jung, while the second was entitled 'Enhancing weather and climate models', the focus of WP2, and was presented by Matthieu Chevallier. A third webinar is planned for early January 2018 and will be given by Doug Smith who will talk about atmosphere-ocean interactions (WP3).

The APPLICATE project is an active participant in the EU Arctic Cluster initiative, participating in important joint outreach activities as the recent Arctic Circle event and in the upcoming Arctic Change and Arctic Futures conferences as well as the ASSW in Davos.

Further dissemination materials will continuously be developed as needed throughout the project lifetime, tailored for specific end-user groups to disseminate project results, inform policies and engage with end-users.

Some foreseen materials include: a biannual newsletter, a series of fact sheets, a series of policy briefs in cooperation with the EU project Blue-Action and the EU Arctic Cluster, a YouTube channel, and possibly further webinars later in the project as more results become available.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background and objectives

One of the objectives of WP7: user engagement, dissemination and training is to increase awareness of the impact of Arctic changes on weather and climate of the Northern Hemisphere by developing relevant forms of communication. The purpose is to increase cooperation and involvement in the project, not least from relevant external stakeholders, and spread the project results to maximise the exposure of the science produced to end-users and the public at large.

To achieve this objective, WP7 has and will develop dissemination materials targeted at specific audiences. These will be used by the projects dissemination team and project partners, to increase and ensure as possible the projects exposure. Further, dissemination materials will be made available and targeted to the public during the project period.

The objective of this report is to summarise the project dissemination materials available as of end of November 2017 and to give an outlook on new and further materials planned to be developed for dissemination.

1.2. Organisation of this report

This report is a follow-up to report D7.5 which gave a summary of the dissemination material available as of May 2017. In the next section a summary of the project dissemination materials available as of November 2017 is given.

Section 3 gives a preliminary outlook of further materials planned to be developed within the project.

The available dissemination materials are shown in the Annexes.

2. DISSEMINATION MATERIALS (as of November 2017)

Dissemination materials have been developed and continuously updated since the start of the project. These are all available and accessible to partners, and the public as relevant, to use through the internal page and the project website, www.applicate.eu.

In addition to the dissemination materials, all the project deliverables labelled as “Public” in the project Description of Action (DoA) are available on the website and through the European portal Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) and can be used to showcase the project.

Table 1: Project dissemination materials for the public as of November 2017.

Dissemination material	Target audiences	Use
Project logo	General public, Project partners	The project logo contributes to define the project identity and is used internally within the project for all written documents (e.g., deliverable reports, meeting summaries, etc.) as well as externally on all presentations and dissemination materials.

<p>Website www.applicate.eu</p>	<p>General public, Project partners, Scientific community</p>	<p>The project website is the primary source of information and reference for the project. It is designed to attract visitors interested in the Arctic and gives general as well as detailed information on the project, its structure and goals, as well as news and events. There is an internal section, with access restricted to project partners, where project documentation (including deliverables, agreements, protocols, etc.) is stored.</p>
<p>Social media</p>	<p>General public, Project partners, Scientific community</p>	<p>Social media channels for the project include Twitter and Facebook. News and events related to the project are announced on social media in addition to the website. Social media is also used to interact with other projects and the rest of the Arctic community as well as to engage with end-users to disseminate project results and products.</p>
<p>Flyer</p>	<p>General public, Stakeholders</p>	<p>The project flyer gives an overview of the project objectives, activities and partners involved. It is designed to attract interest in the project and includes the website address and primary contacts. The flyer will be distributed at conferences and events.</p>
<p>Rollup poster</p>	<p>General public, Stakeholders</p>	<p>The project roll up poster has been designed to be used at exhibitions and events. The poster has a basic design with key information on the project and the address of the website.</p>
<p>Project overview presentation</p>	<p>Project partners, Scientific Community, Stakeholders</p>	<p>A 4-slide overview presentation of the project gives an introduction of the project objectives and the key benefits for society. It can be used alone or integrated by partners in their presentations at conferences. The presentation includes all the partners and the project website.</p>
<p>NEW - Project Poster</p>	<p>Project partners, Scientific Community, Stakeholders</p>	<p>A poster template for displaying project material in an organized format to be used at various conferences and other outreach events. First poster – From Tweeting to Training was presented at the EMS conference. Further posters will be developed for other conferences.</p>
<p>NEW - Blog</p>	<p>General public, Stakeholders</p>	<p>Developed in close cooperation with the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) and the project Blue Action and hosted by the Helmholtz platform, the blog “Polar Prediction Matters” will host articles for and by stakeholders on the scientific outputs of Arctic research and how these can be used/transferred to other societal sectors beyond academia. To a lesser extent, some contributions from scientists are also planned in the blog. Four different articles have been published so far. The first one being a welcome to the blog by the director of the international Coordination Office for Polar Prediction, and three other articles mainly dealing with navigation and risk management & safety</p>

		operations. All these blogposts highlight the use of weather and climate information by different Arctic stakeholders.
NEW - Webinars	Early Career Scientists, Project partners, Scientific Community, General public	A webinar series organised in cooperation with the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) was begun in September 2017. Two webinars have been carried out so far (a general introduction to the project by Thomas Jung and a focus on WP2 science (enhancing weather and climate models) by Matthieu Chevallier). A third webinar is planned for early January 2018 and further webinars may also be organised later in the project as more results become available.
NEW - EU Arctic Cluster www.eu-arcticcluster.eu	General public, Stakeholders	Outreach activity in cooperation with EU-PolarNet, European Polar Board and 6 other large scale Arctic related Horizon 2020 projects dealing with modelling (Blue Action, ICE-ARC), observations (INTAROS), infrastructure (ARICE), permafrost and social impact (NUNATARYUK), and research networking (INTERACT). The cluster is aimed to support and better coordinate outreach activities, stakeholder engagement and data management. Webpages on the EU-PolarNet website, a flyer and booth were developed by the Applicate WP7 team on behalf of the entire consortium. Joint activities (side events, joint attendance to specialized and non-specialized meetings, etc.) are and will continue being planned.
NEW – Article Newsletter PolarPredictNews	General public, stakeholders	An article describing the importance of attending the Arctic Circle Assembly for APPLICATE and the Year of Polar Prediction (YOPP) was written by the partners in WP7. Entitled “Feeling the Arctic to better understand”, it describes the three busy days of dialogue, interactions and learning on priority issues affecting the lives and businesses of people from polar regions that experienced the attendants to the event: international government representatives, statesmen, organizations, corporations and universities, think tanks, indigenous communities and many other actors interested in the Arctic. The article was published in issue 4 of PolarPredictNews, a newsletter developed by the International Coordination Office (ICO) for Polar Prediction.

3. OUTLOOK

Further dissemination materials will be developed throughout the project lifetime, tailored to specific user groups to disseminate project results, inform policies and engage with stakeholders.

Table 2: Further dissemination materials planned to be developed within the project.

Dissemination material	Target audiences	Use
Newsletter	General public, Project partners	A biannual newsletter to be issued by the outreach team through the project website and directly communicated to partners and relevant stakeholders. It will summarise the main project activities and results, reports from events, news, upcoming meetings and deadlines, and vacancies within the project.
Policy briefs	Stakeholders	Developed in collaboration with the EU and the EU project Blue-Action during the latter period of the project, with a focus on business and policy stakeholders, the 2 – 4 envisioned policy briefs will target policy makers and how the scientific results from the two projects (and Arctic research in general) can inform and support policy decisions.
Fact sheets	General public, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	A series of self-explanatory 2-page documents covering a wide range of project-relevant topics in Arctic research, polar prediction and how Arctic environmental changes affect mid-latitudes. Preliminary estimation is 4-6 issues.
YouTube Channel	General public, Scientific Community, Stakeholders	A collection of videos, interviews and animations relevant to the project, scientific results, and activities.

4. REFERENCES

APPLICATE project website: www.applycate.eu

Blue Action project website: www.blue-action.eu

Year of Polar Prediction website: www.polarprediction.net/yopp/

Polar Prediction Matters Blog: <https://blogs.helmholtz.de/polarpredictionmatters/>

EU-Arctic Cluster project website: www.eu-arcticcluster.eu

APECS-APPLICATE webinars:

(1) <https://www.apecs.is/career-resources/webinars/webinar-archive/details/10/157.html>

(2) <https://www.apecs.is/career-resources/webinars/webinar-archive/details/10/157.html>

Article in the PolarPredictNews newsletter:

http://www.polarprediction.net/fileadmin/user_upload/www.polarprediction.net/Home/News/PolarPredictNews/PolarPredictNews04_final.pdf (point 10)

5. ACRONYMS

CORDIS: Community Research and Development Information Service

DoA: Description of Action

YOPP: Year of Polar Prediction

APECS: Association of Polar Early Career Scientists

6. ANNEXES

Dissemination materials

The objective of INTAROS is to develop an integrated Arctic Observation System by extending, improving and unifying existing systems in the different regions of the Arctic. INTAROS has a strong multidisciplinary focus, with tools for integration of data from atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere and terrestrial sciences.

www.intaros.eu

Advanced prediction in Polar regions and beyond

The objective of APPLICATE is to develop enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond, and to determine the influence of Arctic climate change on Northern Hemisphere mid-latitudes, for the benefit of policy makers, businesses and society.

www.applycate.eu

Arctic Impact on Weather and Climate

Blue-Action seeks to understand the linkages between the Arctic and the global climate systems to improve weather and climate modelling and prediction, to improve forecasting of hazardous conditions and climate extremes, and to co-design targeted climate services with relevant stakeholders.

www.blue-action.eu

NUNATARYUK

NUNATARYUK will develop quantitative understanding of the fluxes and fates of organic matter released from thawing coastal and subsea permafrost; assess risks posed by thawing coastal permafrost, to infrastructure indigenous and local communities and people's health; use this understanding to estimate the long-term impacts of permafrost thaw on global climate and the economy.

ARICE

Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium

An international cooperation strategy aiming at improving Europe's Arctic capacities by better coordinating the existing polar research fleet, by offering transnational access to a set of international High Arctic research icebreakers and by collaborating with maritime industry in a "programme of ships and platforms of opportunity".

A polar research consortium with the ambition to co-design a strategic framework to prioritise science, advise the European Commission on polar issues, optimise the use of polar infrastructure and broker international partnerships.

www.eu-polarnet.eu

INTERACT is a circumarctic network of 82 terrestrial field bases in all Arctic countries and adjacent high alpine and forested areas. INTERACT is building capacity for identifying, understanding, predicting and responding to diverse environmental changes throughout the environmental and land-use envelopes of the Arctic.

www.eu-interact.org

Ice, Climate, Economics - Arctic Research on Change

ICE-ARC is a FP7 project that brings together experts in the fields of economics, natural and social sciences, and technology in order to directly assess the environmental, social and economic impact of Arctic sea ice loss. These trans-disciplinary programmes are essential if we are to continue to strengthen the links between science and society.

www.ice-arc.eu

EUROPEAN POLAR BOARD
AFFILIATED PARTNER

The European Polar Board (EPB) is an independent organisation that focuses on major European strategic priorities in both the Arctic and the Antarctic regions. Its members include European research institutes, funding agencies, scientific academies and polar operators.

www.europeanpolarboard.org

Photo: BAS / Photos on homepage; BAS / Arctic Portal

PROVIDING ANSWERS FOR A CHANGING ARCTIC

THE EU ARCTIC CLUSTER

PROVIDING ANSWERS FOR A CHANGING ARCTIC

The Arctic is warming at almost twice the global average rate. This has dramatic environmental, economic, and societal implications, which are likely to extend beyond the high latitudes with profound global consequences and risks. Mitigation and adaptation strategies in the Arctic are thus an integral part of the European Union's wider efforts to combat climate change and to implement the Paris Agreement.

Furthermore, with its commitment to implementing the United Nations (UN) 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, several EU activities taking place in and relating to the Arctic region contribute to the achievement of the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In order to elaborate appropriate policies, including those relating to climate change, sustainable development and innovation, the EU emphasises the need for better understanding of the challenges the high North is facing. For this reason, the EU continues to be a major contributor to Arctic research, investing around €200 million in Arctic-related research over the past decade and maintaining its current funding level under the Horizon 2020 Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020).

EU ARCTIC PROJECT CLUSTER

The EU Arctic Cluster projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme or the European Union's Framework 7 Programme respectively. Please visit our website for the specific grant numbers.

THE EU ARCTIC CLUSTER

Together, the currently funded Horizon 2020 Arctic projects build the EU Arctic Cluster – a network, which merges the most up-to-date findings on Arctic change and its global implications. Its objective is to provide guidance and policy-relevant information and to support the EU in advancing international cooperation, in responding to the impacts of

climate change on the Arctic's fragile environment, and on promoting and contributing to sustainable development. In doing so, the EU Arctic Cluster cooperates closely with policy makers, indigenous peoples, local Arctic communities, business representatives and the European civil society.

Photo: Hironos - Mikael Sjef

FROM TWITTING TO TRAINING: A COMMUNICATION APPROACH TO ADAPT TO A CHANGING ARCTIC CLIMATE

Dragana Bojovic¹, Marta Terrado¹, Isadora Christel¹, Francisco Doblas-Reyes¹, Halldór Jóhannsson³, Gerlis Fugmann⁴, Luisa Cristini⁵

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APPLICATE PROJECT

The APPLICATE project develops enhanced predictive capacity for weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond, determining the influence of Arctic climate change on the Northern Hemisphere.

To provide at the same time scientifically robust and user relevant and usable knowledge about the climate and weather in the Arctic, the project needs to maximise exposure of the science produced to different users and collect and consider feedback from them. APPLICATE thus assures continuous knowledge sharing and knowledge exchange with Arctic stakeholders, including policy makers, businesses and society.

By effectively exchanging information with stakeholders and co-developing the knowledge, APPLICATE assures the stakeholder-relevance of the project results.

COMMUNICATION APPROACHES FOR AN EFFECTIVE KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE

Society is overwhelmed with information and scientists need to compete with the plethora of available data to gain users' attention and understanding. APPLICATE thus employs diverse communication approaches and participatory techniques to deliver its scientific findings. In particular, the information and activities are shaped around three stakeholder groups:

- **Scientific community** – advanced data users who can indicate gaps in scientific knowledge.
- **Public and private sector** – users who can benefit from enhanced operational predictive capacity across time scales.
- **Society at large** – include the general public and communities who possess local knowledge.

LEVELS OF COMMUNICATION IN THE APPLICATE PROJECT

<p>Communication through information DISSEMINATION</p>	<p>PROJECT WEBSITE The website is a primary channel for communicating about the project.</p> <p>applycate.eu</p>	<p>SOCIAL MEDIA Interactive communication channels, such as Twitter, enable engaging with various stakeholders in a two way communication.</p> <p>		
<p>Communication through USER ENGAGEMENT</p>	<p>WORKSHOPS and MEETINGS Promoting the project and disseminating results in international fora of relevant events will strengthen the role of the project as a base of cutting edge research.</p>	<p>USER GROUP Regular meetings and virtual consultations with representatives of stakeholders from different sectors to assure timely response and feedback to the project outputs and help shape them to user relevant products.</p>	<p>INTERVIEWS Interviews with representatives of different stakeholder categories and economic sectors will help better understand their needs and requirements, while improving their understanding of the changes in the Arctic and the role of climate forecast data.</p>	
<p>Communication through TRAINING</p>	<p>WEBINAR SERIES Aimed at early career researchers, but also open to the general public, the webinars will introduce APPLICATE and increase the awareness about the impact of Arctic changes.</p>	<p>ONLINE COURSE Three-month course on Advancing predictive capacity of Northern Hemisphere weather and climate aimed will increase knowledge and improve stakeholders' capacity for using climate and weather data, advancing predictive capacity of the Northern Hemisphere.</p>	<p>SUMMER SCHOOL It will involve young researchers, current and future stakeholders and users of weather and climate data, improving knowledge on the topics, theories and methods applied in the project, and building a network of well-informed future stakeholders in the Arctic.</p>	<p>Apply for SUMMER SCHOOL until 15 September</p>

CONCLUSIONS

By continuously exchanging information and taking into account stakeholder needs via social media, User Group, workshops, meetings, interviews and virtual consultations, APPLICATE will increase the relevance of its research and hence directly improve stakeholders' capacity to adapt to climate change.

The EU Arctic Cluster

Providing answers for a changing Arctic

The currently funded Horizon 2020 Arctic projects together build the EU Arctic Cluster – a network, which merges the most up-to-date findings on Arctic change and its global implications. Its objective is to provide guidance and policy-relevant information and to support the EU in advancing international cooperation, in responding to the impacts of climate change on the Arctic's fragile environment, and on promoting and contributing to sustainable development. In doing so, the EU Arctic Cluster cooperates closely with policy makers, indigenous peoples, local Arctic communities, business representatives and the European civil society.

The EU Arctic Cluster at a glance

- APPLICATE
- ARICE
- BLUE ACTION
- EU-PolarNet
- ICE-ARC
- INTAROS
- INTERACT
- NUNATARYUK

And their associated partner:
[The European Polar Board](#)

APPLICATE

APPLICATE (Advanced Prediction in Polar regions and beyond: modelling, observing system design and Linkages associated with a Changing Arctic climaTE) is a €8 million project, financed by the EU HORIZON 2020 Research and Innovation programme and involves 16 partners from nine countries (Belgium, France, Germany, Iceland, Norway, Russia, Spain, Sweden and the United Kingdom). The project will be carried out over a period of four years.

The multinational and multidisciplinary consortium will work to enhance weather and climate prediction capabilities not only in the Arctic, but also in Europe, Asia, and North America. A focus on the Arctic is important for improved predictions of weather and climate in the mid-latitudes because the changes taking place in the Arctic due to climate change—the retreat of sea ice, warming seas and a warming atmosphere—have the potential to influence weather and climate in the mid-latitudes.

The impacts of severe weather on commerce and infrastructure can be significant, so having adequate tools to predict when and how severe weather systems will affect Europe, Asia and North America is vital to inhabitants of these regions. The APPLICATE project is bringing together an international team of experts in weather and climate prediction to improve climate and weather forecasting models to work on improving prediction tools while expanding and improving observational capabilities in the Arctic.

The APPLICATE project also involves a strong education, training and outreach component in order to train the next generation of experts and raise awareness about the benefits of improved climate and weather forecasting. Members of the APPLICATE consortium will engage with stakeholders who use weather and climate forecasts to obtain constructive feedback, allowing the models and forecasts to be constantly improved and updated, taking into account user needs. Early career scientists in climate-related fields will have the opportunity to participate in a summer school and webinar lectures, while the general public will be able to learn about the project thanks to specially-produced informational videos and publications.

Coordinator:
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Contact:
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Website:
<https://applicat.eu/>

Twitter: https://twitter.com/applicate_eu
https://twitter.com/applicate_eu

THE EU ARCTIC CLUSTER

Photo: Madsen - Mount Sin

Photo: D&B

Photo: D&B

PROVIDING ANSWERS FOR A CHANGING ARCTIC

Photo: D&B

- ★ Providing guidance and policy-relevant information
- ★ Contributing to a sustainable development of the Arctic
- ★ Supporting EU in advancing international cooperation
- ★ Cooperating with:
 - ★ Policy makers
 - ★ Indigenous peoples
 - ★ Local Arctic communities
 - ★ Business representatives
 - ★ The European civil society
- ★ EU has invested around €200M in Arctic related research over the past decade

The EU Arctic Cluster projects have received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme on the European Union's Framework 7 Programme respectively. Please visit our website for the specific grant numbers.

Photo: SAS/ARCTIC CLUSTER - D&B/PHOTOGRAPHY/ARCTIC

www.eu-arcticcluster.eu

awareness due to its powerful damaging impact to the Caribbean Sea and the South of the United States. With regard to activities on board RV Mirai, Irma can be taken as a suitable case showing that the impact of YOPP observations together with the tropical special dropsondes close to the hurricane can reveal much improved forecast precision. Since the hurricane was associated with a deep atmospheric trough that extended from the north of Alaska to the south of the United States, extra radiosondes from RV Mirai probably contributed to detecting the event well in advance and thus helped to improve the hurricane forecast. Extra radiosondes from this summer's RV Mirai cruise are also going to be implemented in the [YOPP Observations Layer](#).

By using an ensemble data assimilation system developed by the Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology (JAMSTEC), data denial experiments will be carried out in the near future in order to estimate the particular degree of improvement to the forecast of events as such these two examples.

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10 Feeling the Arctic to Better Understand – Arctic Circle 2017 Assembly |

(by Marta Terrado and Dragana Bojovic, Barcelona Supercomputing Center, BSC-

CNS) For three busy days of dialogue, interactions and learning on priority issues affecting their lives and businesses, international government representatives, statesmen, organizations, corporations and universities, think tanks, indigenous communities and many other actors interested in the Arctic have come together in Reykjavik, Iceland, for the Arctic Circle 2017 Assembly. No doubt, Iceland's Harpa Centre was an appropriate venue allowing participants to feel being part of the vast, diverse

and extremely complex region that is the Arctic. Maybe to remind attendees that there is no simple solution to a changing Arctic, the Finnish MSV Nordica icebreaker has been situated just a few steps away the conference centre. Tough but magnificent.

Variety of Interest

The event gathered a plethora of stakeholders representing different types of organizations, ways of life – from big city dwellers to reindeer herders and nomads –, and regions all over the Arctic and beyond. People with diverse professional roles – from owners of big corporations interested in financial planning to whale hunters concerned with the subsistence of their community – were shoulder to shoulder in this annual appointment. Participants had also different connections and stakes in the Arctic, ranging from economic interests linked to resources exploitation, over nature conservation to spiritual links to the Arctic territory based in indigenous people's traditions.

Three busy days: The Arctic Circle 2017 Assembly took place from 13–15 October in Reykjavik, Iceland (Photo: Arctic Circle).

with relevant initiatives focusing on the Arctic. One of these initiatives with high relevance for APPLICATE and YOPP is the Arctic Council – the leading intergovernmental forum promoting cooperation, coordination and interaction among the Arctic states, indigenous communities and other inhabitants. Zooming in on Europe, different European H2020 Arctic Projects, including APPLICATE which is part of the EU Arctic Cluster had the opportunity to discuss the future coordination strategy for user engagement and dissemination.

Researchers Meet Stakeholders

The Arctic Circle Assembly also provided a good opportunity for researchers to meet certain stakeholders who help defining priorities in future Arctic research. For projects and initiatives such as APPLICATE and the Year of Polar Prediction, the Arctic Circle provided an excellent platform to link

Merging Science and Tradition

Some priorities identified in discussions during the assembly pointed at the need for reliable sea ice modelling for shipping planning. The use of future scenarios developed in conjunction with shipping companies was especially stressed. Prediction of the snowpack was mentioned to be relevant for reindeer herding, security and skiing, whereas prediction of ocean temperature, acidity and salinity changes could be used for sustainable management of fish stocks contributing to food security. The added value of merging scientific knowledge with traditional knowledge was a commonplace in many speeches.

Global Opportunities but Challenging

A clear outcome of the Arctic Circle Assembly was that climate change in the Arctic will bring many challenges but also many opportunities. We should accept that there is a need for continuous and profound adaptation, trying to make the most of these opportunities, while minimizing negative impacts and preserving Arctic identity above all.

08 The outreach of the impact is global. Just as the
/ motto of the Arctic Circle assembly was: "What
10 happens in the Arctic doesn't stay in the Arctic".

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11 Subtitles to Polar Prediction Animation | The Polar Prediction video animation is now available with subtitles in six different languages.

Thanks to the special engagement of our colleagues Dragana Bojovic, Matthieu Chevallier, Luisa Cristini, Juhyeong Han and Marta Terrado, subtitles have now been added to the Polar Prediction [video animation](#). To turn on the subtitles available in French, Italian, Spanish, Korean, German and English, click on the *Settings* button below the video on the right side (gear wheel symbol) which will bring up options for subtitles.

To read along: The Polar Prediction animation now with subtitles in six different languages.

12 YOPP-endorsed! – CAALC | YOPP endorsement is available for projects, programmes and initiatives that contribute to the aims of the Year of Polar Prediction. More than sixty projects, programmes and initiatives already received project endorsement from YOPP.

The **YOPP-endorsed project “Characterization of Low Clouds and the Atmosphere over the Antarctic Peninsula and West Antarctic Ice Sheet” (CAALC)** is led by the physical chemist Penny Rowe from the NorthWest Research Associates (NWRA, USA) and the University of Santiago, Chile. In close collaboration with Chilean and Korean colleagues who launch weather balloons from the neighbouring station King SeJong, Penny Rowe will carry out radiosonde launches, surface-based radiometry measurements, and balloon-borne in situ cloud property measurements at Escudero station to learn about the atmospheric characteristics over Antarctica. Just before flying out for the upcoming campaign this November, Penny Rowe was so kind to tell us about her project.

Dr. Rowe, what are you going to find out with CAALC?

We hope to improve understanding of clouds and the lower atmosphere above the Antarctic Peninsula and Southern Ocean by making measurement from weather balloons, lidar, and radiation instruments during three summer campaigns at Escudero Station, Antarctica. We also hope these measurements can help determine the degree to which launching weather balloons over Escudero Station (located near the end of the Antarctic Peninsula) will help improve weather forecasting.

Who is working with you, and where do the funds come from?

I'm fortunate to be part of a hard-working and amazing team from the Universidad de Santiago de Chile (USACH), including Raul Cordero, Edgardo Sepulveda, and Alessandro Damiani. This also includes a number of students from USACH that support our project by helping with the instrumentation on our science platform, led by Raul Cordero, at Escudero Station, on King George Island. The funding comes from FONDECYT (Preis

Home > Polar Prediction Matters

Tasmania, Australia. Jan Lieser is a meteorologist and sea-ice ... [\[Read more\]](#)

Category: [Forecast Providers](#), [Forecast Users](#) Tags: [Antarctica](#), [Australia](#), [Search and Rescue](#) Comments: [No Comments](#)

To turn or not to turn

YOPP Polar Prediction Matters

28. November 2017

How the right advice enables informed decisions The Authors: Dr Jan Lieser and Dr Tomas Remenyi are researchers at the Antarctic Climate & Ecosystems Cooperative Research Centre (ACE CRC) of the University of Tasmania in Hobart,

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Polar Prediction Matters to the Icelandic Coast Guard

YOPP Polar Prediction Matters

12. October 2017

The Authors: Snorre Greil, project officer and Soley Kaldal, risk management and safety engineer, Department of Operations, Icelandic Coast Guard. It is getting late and dark in Iceland. The operator in the Icelandic Coast Guard (ICG) operations centre is preparing to broadcast the ... [\[Read more\]](#)

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Aspects of Practical Planning and Management of an Ice Passage About the Author: Captain Uwe Pahl was the master of the German research icebreaker RV Polarstern from 1996

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